

ESG Performance and Project Completion Delays in the Real Estate Sector: A Correlation Analysis

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Abstract:

This study examines the correlation between ESG Scores of real estate developers and extension, lapse and delay in completion of projects undertaken by them. The study utilises publicly available secondary data on ESG Scores and real estate projects. Data is analysed using Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation. The findings show a strong negative correlation between ESG Scores and extensions, lapses and delays in completion of projects. This indicates that developers having high ESG Scores have lower percentage of extensions, lapses and delays in their projects. Moreover, governance and environmental aspects have shown highest negative correlation to extensions, lapses and delays in completion of projects, implying that developers who perform better on these fronts, have lesser extensions, lapses and delays in their projects.

Keywords: Real Estate, ESG, Project Delays

Introduction

There has been an increasing awareness of negative the impacts of a business on environment and society among today's corporates. Corporates are now making disclosures regarding environmental, social and governance practices (ESG). ESG reporting helps to measure the performance of business in environmental, social and governance aspects. Environmental aspects of ESG reporting focus on conservation and minimum wastage of resources, which bring cost savings for the business. Social aspects focus on safety of workforce, working conditions, equality, unionisation leading to reduced labour turnover and greater cooperation. Better Governance practices imply better disclosures, transparency, monitoring, etc helping in better decision making. Thus, ESG indirectly contributes to increasing administrative efficiency of a business. But, adoption of

sustainable practices comes with high upfront cost and it disrupts operations. Also there may not be clarity regarding short term returns of such practices. As a result businesses hesitate in adopting sustainable practices citing increased cost, efforts and time. This paper discusses the link between ESG practices adopted by real estate companies engaged in real estate projects in Pune and delay in completion of their projects. The real state sector in India has been plagued by time and cost overrun issues. The Real Estate Regulation and Development (RERA) Act was passed in 2016 to address these issues. The Act prescribes several mandatory practices to be followed by developers in ensuring timely completion of projects. In this paper the correlation between ESG Scores and timely completion of real estate projects is studied.

Objectives

1. To find out correlation between lapse of real estate projects and ESG scores of developer company
2. To find out correlation between extension of real estate projects and ESG scores of developer company
3. To find out correlation between delay in completion of real estate projects and ESG scores of developer company

Scope:

This paper focuses on listed real estate companies having ESG rating. The projects of this company registered with MahaRERA from 2018 onwards are included. Only those projects for which original proposed completion date has elapsed and those completed before due date form a part of this study. The scope of this paper is used for the geographical area of Pune district only.

Review of Literature:

Georgiadou and Ionica (2025) stated that the prioritisation of environmental factors can deepen both global and local sustainability inequalities. Strong ESG performance has the potential to raise property values, attract investment, and reduce climate-related risks. However there may be failure to address the socio-economic and governance aspects of emerging markets.

Dorri and Shahini (2025) found that in Albania ESG principles are becoming relevant in real estate. Some banks are beginning to show interest in sustainable financing, and a few development projects are experimenting with green building ideas. Challenges include a lack of financial support, vague policies, and limited technical knowledge across the sector.

Yadav (2025) Found that ESG performance is positively associated with firm valuation. Companies with higher ESG scores generally attract a valuation premium relative to their less sustainable peers.

Governance improvements show the most robust linkage to higher valuations, Environmental initiatives also correlate with better valuations. The Social dimension did not show a clear immediate effect on market value.

M. Cajias et al. (2014) stated that high overall ESG ratings positively affect a company's market value. Negative ratings have the strongest effects on company value. A relatively high overall ESG rating affects total returns negatively.

Methodology

Research Design -The study uses a quantitative and correlational research design.

Sources of Data - The study utilises secondary data from the following sources:

1. Data on number of projects registered, completed, lapsed, extended, etc. is taken from the MahaRERA website.
2. Data regarding ESG Ratings is taken from CRISIL ESG Ratings website.

Analysis of Data - Analysis is done using Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation.

Data and Analysis:

Data regarding ESG Scores has been derived from CRISIL ESG Ratings for the year 2024-25. The ESG Scores for individual factors and combined scores are expressed out of total 100.

Data regarding extended, lapsed and delayed projects has been collected from MahaRERA website.

A developer has to declare a proposed date of completion of project on MahaRERA website at the time of registration. However, in case of failure to complete within time, or, if delay is expected to occur in future, the developer can get the date extended. The project receives a Certificate of Extension from MahaRERA.

Extension of project implies greater waiting period for customers as well as increased cost for the project.

Lapse of a project occurs when the developer fails not only to complete the project in time but also to complete the process for project extension. This points towards inefficiency in operations as well as compliance.

The data on delay in projects was compiled by comparing the original proposed date of completion and the date mentioned in Architect's Certificate of Project Completion.

Analysis is done using Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation.

Findings:

1. ESG Scores of the Developers

Following table shows ESG Score of different developers.

ESG Rating					
Developers	E (Environmental)	S (Social)	G (Governance)	Score Range	Remark
Lodha Developers Limited	54	54	73	61-70	Strong
Sobha Limited	30	48	68	41-50	Below Average
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	47	51	71	51-60	Adequate
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	28	36	67	41-50	Below Average
Mean ESG Score		39.75	47	70	

In all the three categories, Lodha Developers Limited has the highest score - for environmental factors (54) social factors (54) and for governance factors (73).

Kolte-Patil Developers Limited has the lowest score for for all three categories- environmental factors (28) social factors (36) and for governance factors (67).

The mean ESG Score for environmental factors is 39.75 , while the mean ESG Score for social factors is 47 and for governance factors it is 70.

2. Number of Projects Extended and Lapsed:

Following table shows extended projects of different developers:

Number of Projects Extended			
Developer	Total Number of Projects	Extended	Extended Projects as % Of Total Number of Projects
Lodha Developers Limited	7	1	14.286

Sobha Limited	3	1	33.333
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	10	2	20
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	11	5	45.455
Mean Extended Projects			2.25
Mean Extended Projects %			28.268

It can be seen that Kolte-Patil Developers Limited has the highest percentage of extended projects i.e., 45.455%. Lodha Developers Limited has the least percentage of extended projects i.e., 14.286 % Mean number of projects extended is 2.25, whereas mean percentage of projects extended is 28.268%.

Following tables shows lapsed projects of different developers:

Number of Projects Lapsed			
Developer	Total Number of Projects	Lapsed	Lapsed Projects as % Of Total Number of Projects
Lodha Developers Limited	7	1	14.286
Sobha Limited	3	1	33.333
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	10	0	0
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	11	5	45.455
Mean Extended Projects			1.750
Mean Extended Projects %			23.268

Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited has the least percentage of lapsed projects (0), whereas Kolte-Patil Developers Limited has the highest percentage of lapsed projects (45.455).

The mean percentage of lapsed projects is 23.268%.

3. Delay In Completion of Projects:

The delay in completing various projects, in months, is as follows:

Number of Projects Completed with Delay in Months				
Developer	RERA Registration No.	Original Date	Actual Date	Delay in Months
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	P52100027791	30/06/2024	22/04/2024	2.3
	P52100033371	31/12/2023	27/09/24	9
	P52100000428	30/12/2021	05/03/202 1	-9.8
	P52100014875	30/06/2020	01/06/202 3	35.5
	P52100018473	30/03/2023	31/03/202 3	0.03
Total				37.03
Lodha Developers Limited	P52100020156	28/02/2027	27/02/2025	0
	P52100020172	30/03/2025	8/4/2024	-11.7
	P52100017082	30/06/2022	9/6/2023	11.3
	P52100020142	30/09/2024	3/3/2022	-30.9
Total				-31.3
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	P52100019375	30/03/2023	24/02/2022	-13.1
	P52100019407	30/03/2023	24/02/202 2	-13.1
	P52100019393	28/08/2023	1/12/2022	-8.9
	P52100030814	28/02/2023	1/12/2022	-3

	P52100000171	30/12/2020	16/03/201 9	-21.5
	P52100016677	30/09/2020	24/06/201 9	-15.2
	P52100016619	30/03/2023	25/09/202 0	-30.1
	P52100019406	28/08/2023	21/03/202 3	-5.3
Total				-110.2
Sobha Limited	-	-	-	0
Total				0

Sobha Limited has the least number of delayed projects (0) and Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited has the highest number of delayed projects (8).

Average Delay			
Developer	Total Number of Projects	Total Delay in Months	Average Delay
Lodha Developers Limited	7	-31.3	-4.471
Sobha Limited	3	0	0.000
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	10	-110.2	-11.020
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	11	37.03	3.366

By dividing total delay in months by number of projects, we get average delay per delayed project. Negative average delay indicates that projects are completed before original proposed date of

completion. Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited has the least average delay (-13.775 months) and Kolte-Patil Developers Limited has the highest average delay (7.406 months).

4. Correlation Between ESG Scores and Percentage of Projects Extended:

We compute correlation between esg scores and number of projects extended using Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for each of the three aspects of ESG.

Correlation Between ESG Scores and Percentage of Projects Extended				
Developer	% of Projects Extended	E (Environmental)	S (Social)	G (Governance)
Lodha Developers Limited	14.286	54	54	73
Sobha Limited	33.333	30	48	68
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	20	47	51	71
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	45.455	28	36	67
Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation		-0.955	-0.953	-0.970

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for environmental scores and percentage of projects extended is -0.955, whereas that for Social scores and percentage of projects extended is -0.953.

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for Governance scores and percentage of projects extended is -0.970

This indicates a very strong negative relationship between ESG Scores and percentage of projects extended. This indicates that developers having high ESG Scores tend to have lower percentage of projects extended. The highest negative correlation is seen between Governance scores and percentage of projects extended. This suggests that developers scoring high on Governance factor tend to have lower percentage of projects extended.

5. Correlation Between ESG Scores and Percentage of Projects Lapsed:

Correlation Between ESG Scores and Percentage of Projects Lapsed				
Developer	% of Projects Lapsed	E (Environmental)	S (Social)	G (Governance)
Lodha Developers Limited	14.286	54	54	73
Sobha Limited	33.333	30	48	68
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	0	47	51	71
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	45.455	28	36	67
Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation		-0.850	-0.818	-0.823

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for ESG Scores and percentage of projects lapsed also shows a strong negative correlation. This indicates that developers having high ESG Scores tend to have lower percentage of projects lapsed.

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for environmental scores and percentage of projects lapsed is -0.850, whereas that for Social scores and percentage of projects lapsed is -0.818.

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for Governance scores and percentage of projects lapsed is -0.823.

The highest negative correlation is seen between Environmental scores and percentage of projects lapsed suggesting that developers scoring high on Environmental factor tend to have lower percentage of projects lapsed.

6. Correlation Between ESG Scores and Average Delay in Completion of Projects:

Correlation Between ESG Scores and Delay in Project Completion				
Developer	Average Delay in Months	E (Environmental)	S (Social)	G (Governance)
Kolte-Patil Developers Limited	-4.471	54	54	73
Lodha Developers Limited	0	30	48	68
Mahindra Lifespace Developers Limited	-11.02	47	51	71
Sobha Limited	3.366	28	36	67
Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation		-0.769	-0.743	-0.731

High negative correlation can be seen between ESG Scores and average delay in project completion. This shows that developers having high ESG Scores complete projects with lesser delay.

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for environmental scores and average delay in project completion is -0.769, whereas that for Social scores and average delay in project completion is -0.743.

The Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation for Governance scores and average delay in project completion is -0.731.

The highest negative correlation is seen between Environmental scores and average delay in project completion suggesting that developers scoring high on Environmental factor tend to have lower average delay in project completion.

Conclusion:

This paper aimed to analyse the correlation between ESG Scores and completion of projects by selected developers in Pune district. The results suggest a strong negative correlation between ESG Scores and percentage of projects extended and lapsed and average delay in completion of projects. This indicates that real estate developers having higher ESG Scores have lesser delays in project completion. Higher ESG Scores imply better governance practices and sustainable practices leading

to saving in time and timely completion. Also, governance and environmental aspects have shown highest negative correlation to extensions, lapses and delays in completion of projects, implying that developers who perform better on these fronts, have lesser extensions, lapses and delays in their projects.

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